

ID	participant	fragment	phrase	code	theme		note			
Case study 1 - Focus group 1 - 9 November 2022										
P1 . P2 . P3 . P4 . P5 . P6										
Goal diagram - i*										
1.1	P1	the hexagon is the goal. I understand	hard symbols interpretation		understandability					
1.2	P1	Yes, these are the resources		consistency with body of knowledge	completeness					
1.3	P1	the context is to	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.4	P5	but probably wait	position of water	more complete elements	completeness		discussione sulla risorsa WATER			
1.5	P5	it's a good suggestion	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.6	P6	whether another	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.7	P5	have the environment	missing object	more complete elements	completeness		discussion: environment as actor			
1.8	P5	I don't have a clear answer like my		more complete elements	completeness		limit represented actors / completeness vs understandability			
1.9	P5	it could make total	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.10	P6	I think in the end	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.11	P1	natural resources	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.12	P1	Introducing an actor as a nature as		more complete elements	completeness		limit represented actors / completeness vs understandability			
1.13	P6	the same blocks that are in the Ostrom		consistency with body of knowledge	completeness					
1.14	P1	the Ostrom actor	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.15	P5	that this diagram	partially clear	understandable	understandability					
1.16	P5	is incomplete because	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.17	P5	try to modify the	missing object	more complete elements	completeness					
1.18	P5	But if we see that this. This diagram		more complete elements	completeness		limit represented actors / completeness vs understandability			
1.19	P5	keep it as simple as possible		more complete elements	completeness		limit represented actors / completeness vs understandability			
1.20	P1	this can be done with layers. So we		multi-layer representation	completeness					
1.21	P2	Task missing on the wireless sensor		more complete elements	completeness					
1.22	P2	decision support	more consistent	more complete elements	i* completeness					
1.23	P5	it is just the the	more consistent	more complete elements	i* completeness		capire se lasciare			
1.24	P1	maybe some con	more consistent	more complete elements	i* completeness					
1.25	P5	The dss infrastru	more consistent	more complete elements	i* completeness					
1.26	P5	the encompassin	more consistent	more complete elements	i* completeness					
Class diagram UML										
1.28	P2	There is also an interaction with the		more complete elements	completeness					
1.29	P5	so probably two class diagrams make		multi-layer representation	completeness		discussion triggered by question: diagramma per il setup del sistema			
1.30	P5	separating the diagram describing		multi-layer representation	completeness					
1.31	P5	highlight different level of skills and		multi-layer representation	completeness					
1.32	P6	So if we specialise, if we somewhat		multi-layer representation	completeness					
1.33	P1	I was also thinking whether we can		useful coloring	understandability					

1.34	P1	what does id and coords mean?	hard symbols interpretation	understandability				
1.35	P1	I think it is very clear.	very clear	understandability				
1.36	P1	Of course we have to make clear	procedure for co-creation needed	methodology				
1.37	P1	is there a software to to design	procedure for co-creation needed	methodology				
1.38	P4	it could be helpful to have kind of a	procedure for co-creation needed	methodology				
1.39	P5	they fill tables	procedure for co-creation needed	methodology				
1.40	P1	If you ask to me, I would say that it	very effective	effectiveness				
1.41	P1	how to link this to the broader conc	consistency with body of knowledge	completeness				
1.42	P1	to identify the critical points for the	cost-benefit analysis support	methodology				
1.43	P3	The arrow between irrigation tool to	hard symbols interpretation	understandability				
1.44	P5	about the comprehensibility. The d	hard symbols interpretation	understandability				
Process diagram BPMN								
1.46	P1	very clear.	clear	understandability				
1.47	P1	Now I think this is a very effective	effective	effectiveness				
1.48	P1	Understanding how precise and hc	tool for analysis	methodology		analisi costi-benefici; interaction with socio-ecological system;		
1.49	P1	but also of the interaction with the	tool for analysis	methodology				
1.50	P1	But then it could be also useful for	multiple objectives of the represer	effectiveness		vista più semplificata		
1.51	P1	Very effective overlapping	effectiveness of visual representat	methodology				
1.52	P2	the idea is from the process model	immediate detection of advantage	effectiveness				

ID	participant	fragment	phrase	code	theme	note
Case study 2 - Focus group 1 - 23 October 2023						
P7, P8, P9, P10						
Class diagram - La						
1.1	P1	la linea mi sembr	diagram reprodu	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	
1.2	P1	Se è tutto a mani	role of the consor	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	RUOLO DEL CONSORZIO ci sono altri frammenti che seguono, come si gestisce questa indecisione. Una possibilità è scrivere che la visualizzazione del diagramma ha subito stimolato la domanda sul cambiamento di scala. Questo è legato al concetto di completezza, loro vogliono un allineamento delle rappresentazione ...
1.3	P1	la APP al momen	add a link from a	more complete elements	UML completeness	
1.4	P1	collegamento tra	add a link from s	more complete elements	UML completeness	
1.5	P1	questo collegam	add a link from s	more complete elements	UML completeness	
1.6	P2	Quindi io la mett	add a link from s	more complete elements	UML completeness	
1.7	P2	questa cosa qui	add a link from a	more complete elements	UML completeness	
1.8	P2	lo stanno facend	link to animal reg	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	LINK ANIMAL REGISTRY discussione su come rappresentare animal registry: manuale o automatico?
1.9	P2	il ruolo del cons	central role of the	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	
1.10	P2	La tecnologia è v	technology testet	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	
1.11	P1	la stiamo svilup	technology devel	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	
1.12	P1	Quindi io terrei il	not change possi	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	lasciare così
1.13	P1	il consorzio potre	bbe moltiplicare q	reuse of the models	methodology	riuso del diagramma con consorzio uguale e altri casefici - il consorzio ha il suo software
1.14	P3	se si legge in que	sta maniera già r	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	
1.15	P3	rappresentare qu	how to represent	more complete elements	understandability vs completeness	
1.16	P1	mi sento che una	understable if yo	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.17	P1	A me sembra mo	very understand	very clear	UML understandability	
1.18	P1	questa cosa di r	supply chain repr	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	
1.19	P1	questa linearità	d linearity of the	su consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness	
1.20	P2	[un utente che non	è esperto di qui	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.21	P1	Ma gli altri Living	diagrams are diff	procedure for co-creation	methodology	
1.22	P3	li faremo, noi far	diagrams creatio	procedure for co-creation	methodology	procedura creazione diagrammi ... inserire in conclusione?
1.23	P4	Facciamo diagra	diagram validatio	procedure for co-creation	methodology	
1.24	P4	il Living Lab non	lo deve vedere, ci	procedure for co-creation	methodology	
1.25	P1	lavorare a livello	di coordinatore	procedure for co-creation	methodology	
1.26	P1	solo con Living Lab	Coordinator	procedure for co-creation	methodology	
1.27	P1	alcuni sono più	ir easy for LL coord	procedure for co-creation	methodology	
1.28	P1	Mi piace molto e	useful coloring	useful coloring	UML understandability	
1.29	P2	Si (confirms -->	il useful coloring	useful coloring	UML understandability	
1.30	P1	le diverse relazio	hard arrow interp	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.31	P1	le frecce, in ques	hard arrow interp	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.32	P1	la leggenda ...	tri hard arrow interp	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.33	P4	poi lì nella legger	simplify use of s	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	discussione se rinunciare ad alcuni simboli per semplificare
1.34	P3	questa distinzione	utility of the leger	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.35	P1	È utile, però si	de use of particular	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.36	P1	si, perché tendia	hard to create de	effectiveness of visual represent	methodology	
1.37	P1	fate con la con	u methodology to	c procedure for co-creation	needs methodology	
1.38	P1	è utile avere un	utility of standard	effectiveness of visual represent	methodology	
1.39	P1	io lo faccio così	difficult comuni	effectiveness of visual represent	methodology	questione della rappresentazione della conoscenza
1.40	P1	io stakeholder no	not understand	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.41	P1	il ricercatore o il	useful for a rease	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.42	P1	potrebbe essere	useful for compa	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.43	P1	i Living Lab non	è useful for a LL	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.44	P1	Una rappresenta	useful to be used	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.45	P1	io la vedo molto	very useful	very useful	UML effectiveness	
1.46	P1	comparazione tri	comparison betw	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.47	P1	i progetti europei	EU research proj	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.48	P3	una rappresentaz	utility of the stanc	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.49	P2	Si, concordo	utility of the stanc	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
1.50	P1	magari è un doc	limitations of real	effectiveness of visual repres	methodology	discussion: text vs visual representation
1.51	P3	la rappresentazi	effectiveness of	effectiveness of visual repres	methodology	
1.52	P1	non tutti sono	caj can be difficult	to hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	discussion: la rappresentazione visuale è più semplice per alcuni, più difficile per altri (percezione di P1)
1.53	P1	capacità a presci	need capacity to	hard symbols interpretat	UML understandability	
1.54	P1	A me piacciono n	appreciation of th	very useful	UML effectiveness	
1.55	P3	se uno ha fatto	u need of an initial	hard symbols interpretat	methodology	discussion: challenge related to curva di apprendimento
1.56	P1	Esatto. Esatto, p	è facilitate informat	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness	
Goal diagram - i*						
1.58	P2	la parte del veter	goal mismatch	more complete elements	i* completeness	discussion: a partire dal goal del vet si è scelto di mettere "salute riproduttiva"
1.59	P4	in realtà lo scopo	animal selection	more complete elements	i* completeness	
1.60	P1	è una delle cose	support of the AP	more complete elements	i* completeness	
1.61	P2	l'animale sia. Inse	missing element	more complete elements	i* completeness	
1.62	P3	questa parte fors	goal or softgoal	more complete elements	i* completeness	
1.63	P2	la parte riprodotti	reproductive mar	more complete elements	i* completeness	
1.64	P2	si	understandable	understandable	i* understandability	
1.65	P1	io ho fatto un po	difficult to unders	hard symbols interpretat	i* understandability	
1.66	P1	manca la parte	(add governance	more complete elements	i* completeness	discussion: add institution / animal registry (vedi anche 1.8)
1.67	P4	in relazione al go	add governance	monitoring policies and intere	i* effectiveness	
1.68	P4	la pallina anche	(add governance	more complete elements	i* completeness	
1.69	P1	il monitoraggio di	role of policy mo	monitoring policies and intere	i* effectiveness	discussion: come l'interoperabilità interessi a chi monitora (es. consorzio). This diagram supports early discussion on strategic aspects
1.70	P3	si	effective	immediate	i* effectiveness	
1.71	P1	secondo me and	immediate for the	immediate	i* effectiveness	
Process diagram - BPMN						
1.73	P3	Si, OK, spiegato	need to explain ti	consistency	BPMN understandability	
1.74	P1	A me questo piac	the overlap befor	immediate advantages detect	BPMN effectiveness	
1.75	P4	E però qui rappri	complete in repr	complete process represent	BPMN completeness	
1.76	P1	dal punto di vista	complete in repr	complete process represent	BPMN completeness	
1.77	P3	c'è una coerenza	coherent repre	consistency	BPMN understandability	discussione: visualizzazione separata
1.78	P1	Certo	coherent repre	consistency	BPMN understandability	
1.79	P2	molto carino, i	color help unders	useful coloring	BPMN understandability	
1.80	P1	questo è molto in	overlapped repre	immediate advantages detect	BPMN effectiveness	

ID	participant	fragment	phrase	code	theme	note
Case study 2 - Focus group 2 - 24 October 2023						
P11. P12 . P13. P14 . P15. P16						
Class diagram - UML						
2.1	P1	a me sembra molto, molto efficace	very effective		effectiveness	
2.2	P1	[a me sembra] ... molto chiaro	very clear		understandability	
2.3	P1	qui io vedo le componenti tecnolog	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.4	P1	sistema cyber-fisico	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.5	P1	già così può essere sufficiente sic	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.6	P1	mettere tutte le componenti tecnol	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	posizionamento centrale della tecnologia
2.7	P1	troviamo un modo di rappresentar	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	LINK ANIMAL REGISTRY discussi soluzione: lasciare animal registry dov'è e mettere un testo sotto che specifica l'obiettivo di collegare i due
2.8	P5	in generale non c'è l'opzione AL	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.9	P5	volendo uno potrebbe fare un diag	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.10	P5	per esempio fai un clic, spariscono	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.11	P5	Allo stato attuale è vero che abbi	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.12	P1	dipende anche da quanto si incasi	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.13	P6	per mostrarlo agli utilizzatori, fargli	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.14	P6	questo diagramma deve rappreser	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.15	P1	rimuovere ogni concetto di opzioni	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.16	P1	Ci potrebbe essere anche un colle	more complete elements		UML completeness	RUOLO DEL CONSORZIO ci sono altri frammenti che seguono, come si gestisce questa indecisione. Una possibilità è scrivere che la visualizzazione del diagramma ha subito stimolato la domanda sul cambiamento di scala. Questo è legato al concetto di completezza, loro vogliono un allineamento delle rappresentazione ...
2.17	P1	[il management software, nella visi	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.18	P1	nell'ottica della interoperabilità que	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.19	P1	sicuramente la pecora è centrale p	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	Qua si sviluppa una discussione e la possibilità di fare più diagrammi
2.20	P1	il software dovrebbe anche poi vec	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.21	P1	farne un'altro in cui c'è il camp	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.22	P1	tracciabilità interne.Tracciabilità es	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	esempio della tracciabilità interno/esterno, diverse aree evidenziate
2.23	P1	come dire, un gateway che fornisc	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.24	P1	qui ci potrebbe essere il discorso il	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.25	P4	il servizio Asl perché non è conten	more complete elements		UML completeness	ruolo veterinary asl
2.26	P1	si tratterebbe poi di capire che tip	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.27	P1	Ecco, su questo aspetto dell'interm	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.28	P2	il principio è quello del data Space	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.29	P2	alla leggenda del diagramma per n	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	
2.30	P5	Perché il e la e l'allevatore pratic	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	discussion: force the notation in favour of understandability
2.31	P1	probabilmente intende quello però	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	
2.32	P1	[questo diagramma era si è si è co	very clear		understandability	
2.33	P1	molto molto utile	very effective		effectiveness	
Goal diagram - I'						
2.34	P1	secondo me è efficace	very effective		effectiveness	
2.35	P5	rispetto ai dati ora per non magari	effectiveness of visual representation	methodology		discussion: centrality of the data, from this representation to other diagrams (e.g. entity-relationship)
2.36	P6	fare una semplice tabellina in cui s	effectiveness of visual representation	methodology		
2.37	P5	è una fase, se uno ingegnerizza il	effectiveness of visual representation	methodology		
2.38	P4	generalizzare la procedura, quindi	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
2.39	P1	qui però c'è la infrastruttura, ma l'	more complete elements	completeness		discussion: non trova app, necessità di centralizzare le tecnologia - deviazione dalla notazione e convenzione per codices
2.40	P5	dovremmo stabilir missing goal dat	more complete elements	completeness		aggiungere goal
2.41	P1	per rappresentare questa cosa io l'	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	
2.42	P5	per rendere l'Information System c	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	
2.43	P4	come nel caso dell'altro diagramm	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	
2.44	P5	la freccia su scan Bluetooth dovret	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	cambiare nel diagramma
2.45	P4	nostra convenzione chela tecnolog	keep the representation simple		effectiveness	
Process diagram - BPMN						
2.48	P1	A me sembra molto efficace questi	very effective		effectiveness	
2.49	P1	qui l'unica cosa è che tutto il proce	high level of detail		understandability vs completeness	discussion: questione delle viste separate per migliorare la leggibilità
2.50	P4	avere una visione d'insieme divent	multiple objectives of the representa		understandability	
2.51	P4	Ah, secondo me è molto efficace E	multiple objectives of the representa		effectiveness	
2.52	P4	questo può essere utile per diciam	multiple objectives of the representa		effectiveness	
2.53	P1	queste rappresentazioni che senz	linearity		understandability	
2.54	P2	me quest'ultimo è abbastanza chi	clear		understandability	
2.55	P3	E anche per me è chiaro	clear		understandability	
2.56	P2	soprattutto vedere cosa succede c	immediate advantages detection		effectiveness	
2.57	P3	la trovo estremamente chiara	clear		understandability	
Methodology						
2.59	P3	potrebbe essere utile anche nel se	tool for analysis		effectiveness	

ID	code	mentioned by	theme	example	
1.1	+	consistency with body of kn	FG1#1;FG2#P1;FG2#P2;FG2#P3;FG3#	UML completeness	it seems in line with what was discussed previously (FG2#P1)
1.2	-	more complete elements	FG1#P2;FG2#P1;FG2#P2;FG2	UML completeness	It is fundamental to add a link between the software agency, the agronomist and the vet. In fact, this relation highlights the information exchange being carried out in co-developing the mobile application, and provides the analysts with a clear indication of the actors directly involved in the design of the system
1.3		multi-layer representations	FG3#P5;FG3#P6	UML completeness	This can be done with layers. So we can have a very simple layer with the minimum elements, and then you can try to add new layers in case you want to understand the system's complexity, but at the same time, you want to digitalise other parts of the broader system
1.4	+	useful colouring	FG1#P1;FG2#P1;FG2#P2	UML understandability	I was also thinking whether we can identify with different colours the digital from non-digital
1.5	-	hard symbols interpretation	FG1#P1;FG1#P3;FG1#P5;FG2#P1;FG2	UML understandability	what do id and coords mean?
1.6	+	useful for comparison	FG2#P1;FG2#P3;	UML effectiveness	It could be useful for every one of us to see the differences among LLS
1.7	+	cost-benefit analysis support	FG1#P1;	UML effectiveness	The diagram can help to identify the critical points for the costs
1.8	+	reuse and adaptation	FG2#P1	UML effectiveness	The consortium could use the same diagram in different situations
1.9	-	more complete elements	FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG1#P5;FG1#P6;FG1	completeness	n the area of the vet there is only milk productivity and milk quality. Actually, the vet is not interested in this. Instead, the vet's goal is the animal health, from the productive and repro- ductive perspective
1.10	+	consistency with body of kn	FG1#P1;FG1#P6;	i* completeness	I see resources,
1.11		keep the representation simi	FG3#P1;FG3#P4;FG3#P5	i* understandability	We should keep it as simple as possible
1.12	-	hard symbol interpretation	FG1#P1;FG2#P1;FG3#P5;	i* understandability	The hexagon is the goal. I understand well?
1.13	+	monitoring policies and inter	FG2#P1;FG2#P4	i* effectiveness	This kind of representation related to the goals helps to establish if there are potential conflicts between the actors.
1.14	+	high level of detail	FG3#P1	BPMN completeness	The process is seen from the perspective of the agronomist, then from the point of view of the vet, from the farmer, from the factory...they are all there, well done
1.15	+	useful colouring	FG2#P2	BPMN understandability	I really like the idea of using the colours, I think this is very intuitive
1.16	+	linearity	FG3#P1	BPMN understandability	these representations with straight lines are clean and very understandable
1.17	+	consistency	FG2#P1;FG2#P3	BPMN understandability	the single views are consistent with each other
1.18	+	multiple objectives of the ref	FG1#P1;FG2#P1;FG2#P2;FG3#P4;	BPMN effectiveness	These representations have at least two purposes because on one side we can have a scientific purpose, so this is the case for analysis of the costs; but then they could be also useful for demonstration, maybe in a simpler version. An interesting companion to the demonstration on the field
1.19	+	immediate advantages detai	FG2#P1;FG2#P4;FG3#P2	BPMN effectiveness	presenting the single point of view, the diagram really shows who has the costs, who has the benefits. In the end, it will emerge thanks to these diagrams
1.20	+	useful analysis tool	FG1#P1;FG3#P3	methodology	it could be useful in different contexts as a tool for analysis
1.21	+	effectiveness of visual repre	FG1#P1;FG2#P1;FG2#P2;FG3#P3	methodology	Visual representation is a good support for memory and is more effective than reading a textual document, which is a more time-consuming activity
1.22	+	reuse of the models	FG2#P1	methodology	we can work on replicability of the models
1.23	+	procedure for co-creation ne	FG1#P1;FG1#P4;FG1#P5;FG2#P2;	methodology	Will the other LLS do the diagrams on their own?

